

The Effect of Pyrolysis on the Mechanical Properties of Carbon Fiber-Reinforced and Stabilized Fiber-Reinforced Phenolic Resins for Carbon/Carbon Composites

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Abstract

Carbon/carbon composites were prepared with phenol-formaldehyde resin, one kind of commercial carbon fiber, and a stabilized fiber which was developed in our laboratory. The effect of pyrolysis on the microstructure, fracture behavior and flexural strength of the composites during the carbonization process was studied. Because of the formation of strong bonding in the fiber/matrix interface, the composites made with stabilized fiber showed catastrophic failure and low flexural strength below carbonization temperatures of 600 C. During pyrolysis the flexural strength decreased with the increase in the carbonization temperature.

Keywords: Carbon/Carbon composite, carbon fiber, stabilized fiber, phenolic resin, microstructure, mechanical properties

1. Introduction

The interest of the aerospace industries in carbon/carbon (C/C) composites has rapidly increased over the past decade[1-4]. Phenolic resins reinforced with carbon fibers can serve as starting materials for the preparation of carbon-carbon composites[5, 6]. The carbonization of these composites results in the shrinkage of, and formation of cracks in, the ultimate carbon matrix[7]. The interaction between matrix and fiber may determine whether the resultant carbon-carbon composite will behave as a brittle, flaw sensitive material, or a tough, thermal stress resistant composite. Therefore, the properties of the matrix as well as the fiber/matrix bonding are important factors in deciding the fracture behavior and the final mechanical properties of the composites. The aim of the present work is to study the effect of the carbonization process (300-1000°C) on the mechanical properties and microstructure of phenolic resin reinforced with a commercial carbon fiber and a stabilized fiber, which were developed in our laboratory[8-10]. The fracture behavior and strength of these composites were also studied and were correlated with the

matrix microstructure. This study also may help in understanding the fracture behaviour and hence the mechanical properties of two kinds of carbon/carbon composites.

2. Experimental

Studies were performed with a commercial phenolic resin, a commercial PAN-based carbon fiber (Grafil XAS, Courtaulds), and a stabilized fiber. The resol-type phenol-formaldehyde resin was commercially manufactured by Chang Chun Petrochemical Industry, Taiwan.

A special grade of acrylic fiber, Courtele fiber (Courtaulds Ltd., U.K.), containing 6% methyl acrylate and 1% (itaconic) acid copolymer was used in this work. A single tow of Courtele fiber contains 6000 strands of 1.1 denier monofilament. The stabilization furnace was divided into four zones (one meter for each zone) and set at temperatures of 190°, 230°, 230°, and 230°C, respectively[10]. PAN fibers passed through the furnace in 2.25 hours.

Unidirectional composites with a fiber volume of approximately 48% were produced by a wet winding technique. Polymer composites were cured at 80°C for several minutes and subsequently hot-pressed at 30kg/cm² and 120°C for 30 min and 160°C for 10 min. The composites were cut to appropriate size and samples were pyrolysed at a heating rate of 1°C/min to different end temperatures ranging from 400°C to 1000°C, increased at 100°C intervals.

Flexural strength of composites was determined by the three-point bending method under A.S.T.M. D790. Fractured composites were examined under a scanning electron microscope (SEM).

A Rigaku X-ray diffractometer with Cu K α radiation as the source was used to determine the d spacing and the stacking size (L_c, stacking height of layer planes) of the resin and the composites. The Scherrer equation was used to calculate the stacking size from the width of the (002) reflection, B:

$$L_c = \frac{k\lambda}{B \cos\Theta}$$

in which $\lambda=0.154$ nm, k is the apparatus constant (=1.0), and B is the half value width of the (002) broadened reflection of carbon. The width increases as the stacking size (L_c) decreases.

Density was measured at 25°C according to the density gradient column method. The density gradient column was prepared with a mixture of *n*-heptane and carbon tetrachloride so that a density gradient of about 1.2-1.6 g/cm³ extended from top to bottom.

3. Results and discussion

The change in open porosity during pyrolysis of different composites made with stabilized fiber (SFRC) and carbon fiber (CFRC) is shown in Figure 1. Open porosity of both composites

Figure 1. Variation of open porosity of two kinds of composites during pyrolysis:
 (□) SFRC, (○) CFRC.

increases very rapidly below 600°C. It has been shown that the main volume change of phenolic resin takes place below 700°C and its volume remains almost constant[10, 11]. The volume change is due to the shrinkage of the matrix resin during pyrolysis.

It is known that the appreciable matrix shrinkage that occurs during carbonization generates pores and cracks. Differences between the coefficient of thermal expansion of the fibers and matrix also generates internal stresses and stress cracks on cooling[12]. The level of thermal expansion along the carbon fiber axis is very low. Because the carbon fibers were manufactured at a temperature of over 1300°C, they are stable during the carbonization stage of CFRC. Therefore, the matrix shrinkage promotes the formation of pores and cracks in the CFRC during pyrolysis.

Another reason, the abundant functional groups on the stabilized fibers affects the shrinkage of the matrix resin. The functional groups like C-OOH, C-OH, and C=O are introduced on the backbone of the ladder polymers in the stabilized fibers after the stabilization process[13, 14]. The functional groups of the stabilized fibers will react with the functional groups of the matrix resin during the SFRC curing process. When the fiber and the matrix bonds strongly, the shrinkage of matrix in relation to the fiber in the composite will be blocked during the carbonization process. Therefore, the formation of open porosity in SFRC is restrained. The open porosity of CFRC is higher than that of SFRC.

Above 600°C, the open porosity of SFRC gradually decreases. Above this temperature, the isotropic carbon structures are formed gradually from glassy carbon structures in the matrix, and turbostratic carbon structures are formed from carbon basal planes in the stabilized fibers at the same temperature range. At the same time, the chemical bonds between fibers and matrix are slowly transformed into a carbon structure of an unknown type. For the composites made with

carbon fiber (CFRC), the porosity decreases sharply above 600°C and then increases again above 700°C, as shown in Figure 1. This is due to the weaker bonding between the fibers and the matrix. On pyrolysis, the matrix will shrink away from the fibers with slight displacement of the fibers, resulting in gaps at the fiber/matrix interface. This reaction promoted the formation of porosity in the composites made with carbon fiber. However, in the composites made with stabilized fiber (SFRC), the fiber/matrix bonding, being of a chemical nature, is quite strong. In these composites, the matrix does not leave the fibers during pyrolysis. This is why neither fiber/matrix debonding nor gaps have been observed in such composites.

The density of the samples vs. pyrolysis temperature is shown in Figure 2. The density of the two composites and the resin decreases below 400°C. This is due to the condensation reaction in the matrix, which leads to gas evolution from the resin. Above 400°C, the polymer structures in the matrix are gradually transformed into glassy carbon structures, which then change into isotropic carbon structures above 600°C. Therefore, the density of both of the composites as well as of the resin increases above 400°C.

Figure 2. Variation of density of two kinds of composites, resin, and stabilized fibers during pyrolysis.

For the stabilized fibers, density increases very rapidly below 800°C. This is due to the crosslinking of the ladder polymers as well as the lengthening and broadening of the carbon basal planes, which leads to the repacking of the structure in this fiber. But after this temperature, the density increase is followed by a drop. This is due to the conversion from open to close pores in this fiber[10]. Due to the closure of the fiber surfaces, the penetration of solvents from the fiber surfaces into the inside of the structure is impeded. This results in a decrease in the measured density.

Table 1 shows the X-ray diffraction results of the resin and two composites heat-treated to various temperatures. For the resin, the 2θ is 19° and the half-width of the peak is 11.0° at 300°C , and the 2θ shifts to 18° and the half-width of the peak decrease to 6.5° at 400°C ,

indicating that the condensation reactions occurring in the polymer structures initiate crosslinking and form the glassy carbon. For the composites made with the stabilized fiber, the 2θ is 24.2° at 300°C and 25.0° at 400°C . This is due to the crosslinking of ladder polymers in stabilized fibers and the condensation reaction in the resin. Above 600°C , the half-width of this peak decreases with increasing carbonization temperature. This is due to the lengthening and broadening of carbon basal planes from ladder polymers in the fibers and the formation of turbostratic carbon structures from glassy carbon in the resin. Because of the formation of carbon basal planes, this reaction promotes the increase in preferred orientation of the fibers[13]. Therefore, the half-width of (002) reflection decreases with increasing temperature. The composites made with carbon fiber have the same results.

Table I X-ray diffraction results of the resin and the composites made with stabilized fiber (SFRC) and with carbon fiber (CFRC) treated to various temperatures

	Carbonization temperature ($^\circ\text{C}$)				
	300	400	600	800	1000
Resin					
interlayer spacing d (nm)	0.466	0.492	0.353	0.348	0.355
2θ (degree)	19	18	24	24.8	24.4
half-width (2θ , degree)	11.0	6.5	5.6	6.2	6.4
Stacking size, Lc, (nm)	---	---	1.61	1.46	1.41
SFRC					
interlayer spacing d (nm)	0.367	0.356	0.353	0.348	0.355
2θ (degree)	24.2	25.0	25.2	25.5	25.1
half-width (2θ , degree)	4.5	5.0	6.0	5.9	5.0
Stacking size, Lc, (nm)	---	1.81	1.50	1.53	1.81
CFRC					
interlayer spacing d (nm)	---	0.349	0.353	0.350	0.342
2θ (degree)	---	25.5	25.2	25.4	26.0
half-width (2θ , degree)	---	5.0	5.3	5.4	5.0
Stacking size, Lc, (nm)	---	1.82	1.72	1.60	1.82

Figure 3 illustrates the temperature dependence of flexural modulus of the composites made with stabilized fiber (SFRC) as well as carbon fiber (CFRC) during carbonization. The flexural modulus of both composites decreases with temperatures up to 400°C , and then increases up to 900°C for SFRC and to 800°C for CFRC. The composites (SFRC) exhibit slight drops in the flexural modulus below 400°C . This finding is due to the condensation reaction of polymer structures in resin and the crosslinking reaction of ladder polymers in the stabilized fibers in SFRC. The flexural modulus of composites (CFRC) show sharp drops below 400°C , which is due to the condensation of the matrix resin. After 400°C , the formation of carbon basal planes from ladder polymers occurs and leads to an increase in the preferred orientation, the density, and the modulus of the stabilized fibers[13]. After this temperature, the glassy carbon structures are formed in the matrix resin. Above 600°C , these structures are transformed to isotropic carbon structures. These reactions lead to an increase in the flexural modulus of the composites.

Figure 3 Effect of heat-treatment temperature on flexural modulus of composites during carbonization: (□) SFRC, (○) CFRC.

Figure 4 Variation of flexural strength of composites (SFRC and CFRC) with carbonization temperature: (□) SFRC, (○) CFRC.

Figure 4 shows the temperature dependence of flexural strength for the two composites, SFRC and CFRC, from the curing stage to 1000°C. On pyrolysis, the composites (SFRC) show decreased strength, being weak up to 600°C, and then show increased strength above 600°C.

In the present article, the composites were carbonized to 1000°C. We found that strong interface bonding was formed between the fiber and the matrix in the composites made with the stabilized fiber (SFRC). Therefore, we believe that the interface structures between the fiber/matrix will change to graphite structures when the composites are carbonized above temperatures of 2500°C. The abundant graphite structures between the fiber/matrix may stop the stress and disperse the growth of the crack. As the result of the crack branching, high strength and a pseudo-plastic fracture pattern could be achieved. However, we are still working to confirm this now.

Acknowledgements

Professor Ko also is especially grateful to the National Science Council of the Republic of China for its financial support of this project (No#: NSC 80-0405-E035-04).

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